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AND RESEARCH AREA

PROCEEDINGS

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О ПИСМЕНОСТЪ**

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IN
THE EUROPEAN EDUCATIONAL
AND
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И
НАУЧНО ПРОСТРАНСТВО**

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IN
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SUPERNATURAL FORCES AND MYTHOLOGICAL ELEMENTS IN BULGARIAN AND ITALIAN MYTHOLOGICAL IDEAS: COMPARISON AND ANALOGIES OF SELECTED IMAGES

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Abstract: *The mythological conceptions of different cultures, apart from their specificities, often have their similarities, which are sometimes even more than the differences. Mythology is rich in supernatural beings that reflect the beliefs and cultural characteristics of a people. In this context, Bulgarian and Italian mythology offer interesting analogies and similarities in their supernatural entities that intertwine with the customs, beliefs, and folklore of their societies. A first glance reveals that Bulgarian and Italian mythologies have rich traditions of supernatural forces and mythological elements that have shaped their cultures and narratives over the centuries. And as noted, although each mythology has its own unique characteristics, there are also similarities and shared motifs between them. In the present material, based on various studies, an attempt will be made for a brief comparison and general analysis of the similarities and differences of some of the most common characters existing in the Bulgarian and Italian folk representations, which are not only preserved, but still alive today.*

Keywords: *supernatural, myth, mythology, popular ideas, Italian superstitions, folk superstitions*

Introduction

The mythological representations of the Southern European peoples have their own specificity and peculiarities, which are rooted in the heritage left over from the period of Antiquity. To a large extent, ancient Greek mythology underlies these views. In all peoples and cultures, supernatural beings are perceived as those that are considered to be beyond the ordinary scope of natural laws, ordinary human experience and observation. They are fulfilled with mysticism and incomprehensibility. They are also connected with the understanding of the existence of supernatural forces that move and define them. Beliefs preserve the conviction and notion that these forces not only have different characteristics and incarnations but can also take on new ones constantly and various forms of presentation. What exactly they are and how they are explained, individual cultural and religious beliefs differ. They reveal a particular specificity. A quick review of the literature reveals that in individual societies and nations, understandings of supernatural and mythological beings are found mostly as characters in folklore, legends, and stories. To a lesser extent we find them in religious texts. In later years, however, their popularization was often carried out through various literary works. All these combined places them as part of the traditional culture of the peoples. They appear in popular representations, descriptions and perceptions of various supernatural beings e.g., demons, vampires, werewolves, spirits, ghosts. There are also angels, fairies, elemental beings (spirits of nature), gods and many others. About the frenzy about them is that they are something difficult to explain, but possessing a unique look, characteristics, and abilities. It is inimitable, different, and distinguished in the world around us. There is a point of contact with animals or people, but it is small. The differences are more. They often cannot be fully explained. How can this be explained? Encoded in people's ideas is the understanding of the existence of a symbolic or real presence of the spiritual, mystical, or unknown in the world. Everyone seems to understand that in one way or another these creatures influence people, events, and the environment. However, to what extent this is openly acknowledged and expressed is a separate question. But the idea of them is maintained, which finds expression in the frequent use of elements of fantastic stories, legends, and mythologies, with which human fears, hopes and beliefs

are substantiated or mirrored. It is important to point out that mythical creatures often explain not only social phenomena but are also used as examples related to moral lessons. Various human qualities are indicated, whichy consume through a symbolic or allegorical way. They are instructive or set as an example – it depends on the specific situation and character. However, everything leads to the belief that their presence is important for the cultural identity and worldview of a given community, for its self-expression. That is why this makes them important from the point of view of tracing their presence in the cultural and religious heritage formed over the years [1], [2], [3], [4].

Exposure

Indeed, how are we to single out and understand who these beings are that we define as supernatural and mythical? Are there differences between them? How do they form identity and lay the foundations of folk psychology?

As already stated, supernatural forces are considered to be those that are defined as incomprehensible, surrounded by unknown and mystery, without being able to understand where they come from. They are said to be supernatural in nature and come from other worlds. This is also the reason why their manifestations cannot be explained by the laws of nature. These forces have the ability to transform, to be always different. They also have inexplicable and difficult to predict behavior. Scientific knowledge cannot exist for them and define them completely. There is no exact explanation of what made them appear and why they are there. In turn, mythical forces are different. They connect with something legendary, something that is hard to imagine, but at the same time give us confidence and support. In the old beliefs, it is said that the mythical power is inherent mostly to gods and demigods. That is why it is associated with the heroes who are characters from those ancient legends. They have their own symbolism and often their manifestations have an impact on natural phenomena, wars, people's destinies and the like [5].

The concepts of supernatural and mythological forces that exist in the minds of the southern peoples, including the Italian and the Bulgarian, are based on characters related to ancient Greek mythology. Here we find two of the most recognizable mythical creatures – Scylla and Charybdis. They are an invariable part of the characters that are often mentioned in numerous legends and lore. Both inhabit the sea waters and wreak havoc on mariners and ships. They surround the Strait of Messina, which separates Sicily from the main Italian coast. Scylla is a rock shoal described as a monster that has six heads and long legs. It emerges from the rocks and impetuously attacks the passing ships, capturing the sailors with each of its heads. He lives near the Italian coast. Charybdis is the water vortex that creates huge eddies and swallows deeply everything that falls into them. It is located near Sicily. What both monsters have in common is that they are perceived as obstacles that any sailor wishing to cross these seas is forced to overcome. Homer describes that they stand in the way of Odysseus, who made an attempt to pass through the narrow strait between Sicily and the Italian coast. Seeing these mythical creatures, he was forced to decide how to get past them. Although typical of ancient Greek mythology, representations of both monsters are found in the folklore of various cultures. In Italian it is characteristic because of the place that legend tells that they inhabit. In Bulgarian mythology, which emphasized experiences the influence of the ancient Greek, the two monsters transform into other similar ones. Common is the habitation of the water basins, including the sea (Evsinski Pont – Black Sea) and they pose a danger to all those moving on water. Bulgarian representations talk about water nymphs, mermaids, and other sea spirits. Like Scylla and Charybdis, they are described as beings whose purpose is to attract, deceive and devour sailors, as well as sometimes causing disasters to sailing boats and ships. Any sailor could face them in combat [6].

In the following centuries intraditional for Bulgarians, like other peoples, understandings about new supernatural and mythical powers continue to be formed. Gradually, they became an integral part of people's lives and beliefs. And they play an important role in the formation of cultural identity and worldview. It can be assumed that the main way of their transmission through the generations is through legends, traditions, fairy tales. They also find their expression through various customs and rites. In later years, they are found described in separate literary sources.

Similarly, the Italians also incorporated the supernatural and the mythical as part of its cultural tradition. There are many beliefs in unexplained things, for which explanations are sought, which reveal their idea of how something that was initially declared inexplicable can be understood. A series of factors, including regional, religious, and historical factors, influence the perception.

What are the main aspects that influence and shape the ideas of Bulgarians and Italians regarding supernatural and mythical forces? Several researchers are trying to answer these questions. Foundations and common roots are sought in the past of individual peoples. The mixing of cultures brought about by the movements of compact groups of people in different years is cited as a reason for making general analogies.

Bulgarians have a wide range of ideas about beings, which to a large extent are deeply rooted in folk beliefs and form part of the understanding, respectively folk psychology. The Bulgarian folklore tradition is accompanied by numerous legends and tales about mythical creatures. The most common characters are those of vampires, ghosts, werewolves, dragons, werewolves. There are others. The stories told about them are often used to explain the causes of some of the phenomena in nature. Beliefs in witches and the magic they do, as well as the practice of magical rites are also encountered. This is usually associated with negative energy. People believe that witches can cause illness, misfortune, or performing magical rites for protection and well-being. In Bulgarian traditional beliefs, a special place is given to the idea of a world inhabited by spirits. The understanding is that regardless of whether they are good or bad, human life is accompanied by them. In many places, people believe that the spirits of ancestors and various spirits of the natural elements can directly influence their lives. All this provokes the existence of a series of rites and customs, as well as related ritual practices, which are aimed at protection from evil forces and diseases. This gives rise to the need for and works noof special amulets on which magical symbols are painted. They are worn by people or placed in certain places for protection. Ritual actions also exist with them. Special prayers are offered aimed at protection from troubles, diseases, bad people, dangers. Such a ritual can be seen even in the Orthodox tradition. Known are the so-called Cyprian prayers, which are read only by certain priests and not everywhere. The understandings of the Italians are largely like those of the Bulgarians. However, some important factors also have an influence. First, the Italian culture includes many folklore and mythological elements, in which various mythical creatures come as legends from antiquity. They talk about the mythical creatures in the sea, in the mountains. Also important are those related to volcanoes and their inexplicable power for humans. There are many legends about the volcanoes Vesuvius and Etna. Superstitions say that they were inhabited by various mythological creatures, who with their manifestations had a strong influence on the local people. Regarding other supernatural beings, certain differences are also observed in the individual regions of Italy. The common is related to the notions of existing witches, spirits, giants. All of them have strong destructive abilities, from which people experience problems. As a fight against them, the making of amulets is widespread here. Various methods of protection against evil forces or diseases are practiced. The specific thing is the making of special candles, which is already connected with certain religious rituals. This is influenced by the influence of the Catholic religion on people. It is important to bear in mind that Catholicism contributed to the formation of modern culture and beliefs of the Italians. Traditional ideas are mixed with religious ones. Many people believe in the existence of saints and angels, who are considered supernatural intercessors and helpers in difficult times and in everyday life. There are prayers during which special candles are lit. The practices that accompany these rituals are different. The basis is the understanding that the home must always be protected, and therefore they are often performed in it.

As a summary, it can be stated that with both peoples – Bulgarians and Italians, the formation of cultural identity and in the behavior of people in everyday life is based on understandings preserved from the past, which have undergone certain changes, but have remained deeply rooted in folk psychology and determine people's behavior over the years.

What are the most common images that cover the ideas of Bulgarians and Italians about

supernatural and mythical beings and what comparisons and analogies can be made? Based on various studies [1], [5], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], which highlight similarities and differences, we will look at some of the most typical characters that are present in the folklore of the two peoples and have its roots back in the years:

– **Dragon (flying and fire-breathing creatures)**

These are some of the most ancient creatures known in the folklore of almost all European nations. They are associated with the belief about mythical animals that live in inaccessible places, are covered with scales, can fly and spit fire. They have extraordinary power. A peculiarity is that in most mythologies it is associated with protection from various dangers. In this way, dragons and dragons are not completely accepted as evil creatures. In the Bulgarian public consciousness, they are powerful beings. They help certain people by guarding places associated with some sacredness. Few are allowed to see them. For Bulgarians, the dragon is often compared to a llama (лама), which, however, has more than one head. It guards wealth, treasure, or something sacred. It also protects against dangers. Italian mythology is more about dragons. Here, too, they connect with possessed power and assist people in their struggle to defeat evil. Therefore, they are taken as symbols of war and protection. In the Middle Ages they were part of heraldry. We find them painted or engraved as ancestral symbols. They are located on used armorial bearings, including coats of arms and shields. In church symbolism, however, the dragon has another meaning. He is associated with St. George. It is believed that through the saint's ritual victory over this mythical being, it initiates the mastery of the animal aspect in man and the activation of the divine principle that everyone carries. As a conclusion, it can be stated that Bulgarians and Italians have similar ideas about the mythical creature of a snake/dragon. It is a protector with its supernatural power. The aspiration is that it should always be mastered on the side of good, so that it can bring benefits to people.

– **Witches and related witchcraft**

Witches and the various spells performed by them are present in Bulgarian folklore. Different names were used for them in the individual regions. They possess supernatural and magical power. The visual image is of an old and ugly woman who looks with “evil eyes” and performs magical rituals incomprehensible to those around her. They are associated with causing harm and trouble to people. Interestingly, there are also cases in which women designated as witches do not necessarily bring only evil. There is no bad meaning in the name itself. In some regions they are called healers who use different herbs or things related to animals. They chant and cast spells when they prepare medicines (илачи) with which they heal. Some perform ritual “bullet casting” or “wax casting” by which they take away the evil forces attacking a certain person. These women have inexplicable abilities with which they can perform magical rituals affecting the fate and health of the people to whom they are directed. And yet, the name “which” is also used for them. This shows that in the Bulgarian folklore tradition witchcraft often has a double side – positive and negative. Italian folklore also contains the notion of various witches and wizards. And here these are women who practice magic and can use their powers for both good and evil purposes. In fairy tales and legends, they are often depicted as figures of mystery and intrigue. They are called “strega” (in singular) or “streghe” (in plural), which translates as “leads”. In the individual regions of Italy, the visual image of witches is different. In Sardinia, these are old women who can assume different forms, including animal forms. They are called “Koga” or “Brusha”. In Sicily witches are called “Mayare”. Under the name “Mask” they also exist as a character in the Piedmont region. The knowledge of witchcraft is passed down from mother to daughter and in most cases is related to herbalism, making potions and cures. Elsewhere, there is Jubiana, who does bad things and scares children.

Everything stated up to this point shows that the understanding of witches and the magical rituals they perform are almost the same among both Bulgarians and Italians. In most cases, the similarities are related to what people mean by character aof a witch, an old woman who performs practices incomprehensible to other people. He can heal, but he can also do spells related to doing evil to people. In traditional fairy tales, these images mostly represent bad things and are meant to scare young children. They are often used with an educational character related to the introduction

of moral and legal norms and obedience. In Italian folklore, as well as in that of other Catholic nations, there is also a „magician“ who is a man and can do the same magic as women. In the Bulgarian traditional representations, there is no exactly analogous male character who is the bearer of magical abilities and is like the witches of Western representations. There are healers and those who cast certain spells, but they are not defined by concepts and characteristics typical of witches.

– **The character of Baba Yaga**

Being close to that of witches and sorcerers, the image of Baba Yaga is one of the most interesting and at the same time the most popular in the traditional representations of many peoples. She is known as the character associated with a woman who is invariably present in many fairy tales. Sometimes it resembles that of witches. Interestingly, it has an almost legendary character. Baba Yaga is not directly present in Bulgarian folklore. It is mostly borrowed in fairy tales from the Slavic peoples. It is most prevalent in Russian folk tales. There, Baba Yaga is a mysterious, often misunderstood, and mystical old woman. Everywhere she is perceived as an old and evil witch with incredibly strong magical abilities. She lives somewhere deep in the woods, and it is hard to find her house. It is made of wood, but it is not laid directly on the ground, but is placed on chicken legs that come out of it. Around her, there are often many small mythical creatures like spirits that prevent a person from reaching the house. In turn, Baba Yaga attracts small children. When she meets them, she puts them through various tests. It is precisely under the influence of Slavic folklore, which has deeply penetrated Bulgarian folklore, that Bulgarians perceive her as a fairy-tale character, but compared mostly to that of witches. And while there are analogues in the Bulgarian folklore tradition, there is no exact equivalent in the Italian one of Baba Yaga, the way we find it in Bulgarian under the influence of Slavic folklore. Italians have various other characters who are a known equivalent of Baba Yaga. Among the typical figures, we can mention that of Strega Nona. In southern Italy, this is what a witch with magical abilities was called. She is presented as a woman with a good-natured character, but sometimes she is capricious, as a result of which she does bad things. Despite the fact that she is not quite similar to the Slavic version of Baba Yaga, the closeness comes from the presence of magical abilities. The image of another woman – La Befana, is interesting. It is known throughout Italy. She is perceived as an old woman again. It is typical of her that she flies on a broom at night. This happens around the Christmas holidays. Unlike other similar women, she is good-natured and friendly towards people and especially towards children. Bring them gifts. It outlines them for good. In this way, it represents a complete antithesis of the other images.

The above reveals that the character of Baba Yaga exists, albeit presented in a different light. He is not completely typical of Bulgarians and Italians, but under the influence of foreign tales, he has gradually entered people's imaginations. However, it stands out with its specificity, which makes it difficult to compare. In Bulgarian and Italian folklore, such images always possess magical and unpredictable behavior. They appear as helpers or obstacles to heroes in various tales and legends. Their focus is on imparting moral lessons, presenting trials and challenges for the characters, as well as their ability to reflect societal fears, beliefs, and values of traditional culture.

– **Spirits of nature**

These are perhaps the most frequently encountered images in the mythological representations of various peoples. They exist in Bulgarian and Italian folklore. In Bulgarian mythology, the most common are “samodivas” and “mermaids”. The understanding about them is that these are women who inhabit forest spaces and meadows and are always near a river or lake. The popular image describes them as beautiful girls who often dance and sing. They hunt young men and kidnap them, forcing them to live in their unknown to ordinary people life and world. There are many cases where these samodivas are also associated with the attraction of natural phenomena such as storms and hurricanes. Sometimes they also interact with dragons who protect and assist them. That is why it is not advisable to meet them, and one should avoid the places they are believed to inhabit. In the imagination of the Italians, such creatures are the “nymphs”. These are also beautiful maidens who secretly perform ritual dances at early dawn. One cannot find them easily. Nymphs are considered the patronesses of nature and are usually represented as protectors of the places where they live and

therefore do not allow mortal man near them. And here they are connected with certain remarkable places or phenomena in nature. Italian folklore contains another character that often runs parallel to that of the nymphs. It is about the forest gnomes (nani). Although their gender is not mentioned, it seems to assume that he is male. They inhabit forests, lakes, and mountains. They help people and do not hinder them. They even live next door to them. They play a role in shaping the natural world and exert a beneficial influence on human affairs. They are extremely often present in fairy tales, where in most cases they have a good-natured, although sometimes not completely understandable, character. Being surrounded on all sides by the sea, Italy also contains specific images that correspond to this. The “sirens” can be mentioned here. They are typical creatures of all sea peoples. They are described as beautiful and dangerous creatures in female guise who deceive their mariners with songs and charms. They lure them into their sea world.

In conclusion, it can be stated that there are many similarities and analogies between the images in the traditional Bulgarian and Italian representations of the beings defined as spirits of nature. They contain charm and enchantment. They show the advantages and beauties of the world invisible to the eye of the common man. They are mysterious. If a person touches them, he always remains closed in the world they inhabit. Despite the differences in specific folkloric expressions, these creatures share many commonalities and themes that reflect humans' relationship with their natural environments.

– Vampires and goblins

In Bulgarian mythological representations, vampires are creatures that carry the characteristics of the undead – those for whom life continues even after death. They are the result of a kind of magic. They always appear at night. They represent the dead rising from their graves at night and seeking for food the blood of the living. The vision for them is that they have the ability to change shape and cause bad things or harm to the living. In some areas they are also called “vurdulacs”, and in others they are also likened to “goblins” or “karakonjuli”. They also have the characteristic of disembodied beings. Man is afraid of them and makes rituals to avoid meeting them. There are ritual practices associated with beliefs that should be performed on a deceased person to prevent him from becoming a vampire. In Bulgarian and Italian mythology, the vampire (vampiro) is a disembodied and undead being. They are always associated with death, betrayal, and bloodshed. It originates from humans, and for some it is a continuation of its path after death. But this time there is a curse attached to it. Italians refer to vampires as “werewolves”. Their main manifestation is to feed on the blood of living people. Italians believe that vampires are creatures that seek to influence human life negatively. That is why there are a series of rituals performed so that they do not approach living people and do not enter their houses.

We can assume that in both mythological systems – the Bulgarian and the Italian – the superstitions related to vampires are similar and close in nature. No significant differences were observed. This shows that the idea of vampires among southern European peoples is similar.

It should be noted that in a number of meanings associated with supernatural beings are assimilated and passed in modern Bulgarian literature. This process of inheritance Ivan Granitsky defines as “the energy of the Bulgarian spirit” [12]. Mythological creatures are used to personify different states or, as in Radičkov's work, to certify the space of memory and its importance. On the other hand, again to Ivan Granitsky belongs the respectable study of the compositional features of the image. But in fine art [13]. Here, as in literature, the image, which comes from folklore, is actively used not only as a necessary tradition, but also as an expressive means and device.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be noted that the comparative review and search for analogies among some of the most common supernatural and mythical creatures preserved to this day in the Bulgarian and Italian folk memory reveals a sharing of common themes and beliefs. And although there are differences in the specific folklore figures and stories, there are too many similarities. Common themes and motifs are revealed that are rooted in the communities' beliefs and traditions.

Italian and Bulgarian folklore is enriched with a series of mystical creatures. There are many nature and domestic spirits, forces living in the world around us, but often invisible to the ordinary human eye. These creatures are associated with ideas about the beauty and magic of nature. Some are listed as bad, evil, but there are also those who protect families and homes.

The commonality between Bulgarian and Italian folklore is related to the understanding of the importance of nature and the relationship of people with it in their cultures over the centuries. Both peoples perceive mystical beings as accompanying their life cycle of development. They are full of mystery and magic. They are veiled by the incomprehensible. The inexplicable is often personified with the mystical. The search for the supernatural complements these points. They bear symbolism accompanying the beliefs, fears and values of the communities that created them. It is important to note that all mythical figures preserved in popular memory play a key role in various folklore traditions and rituals. And today, a large part of them is practiced in communities across time and space. Thus, the common features in the mythical world of Bulgarians and Italians not only reflect the similarities in their natural environments and cultural influences, but also emphasize their common human need for connection with the invisible world, as well as the belief in the forces that rule this world. And on the basis of comparative analysis, we gain a deeper insight into the diverse cultural expressions and shared mythological heritage of different societies.

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СВРЪХЕСТЕСТВЕНИ СИЛИ И МИТОЛОГИЧНИ ЕЛЕМЕНТИ В БЪЛГАРСКИТЕ И ИТАЛИАНСКИТЕ МИТОЛОГИЧНИ ПРЕДСТАВИ: СРАВНЕНИЕ И АНАЛОГИИ НА ПОДБРАНИ ОБРАЗИ

Резюме: *Митологичните схващания на различните култури освен спецификите си, често имат свои прилики, които понякога дори са повече от разликите. Митологията е богата на свръхестествени същества, които отразяват вярванията и културните особености на даден народ. В този контекст, българската и италианската митология предлагат интересни аналогии и сходства в своите свръхестествени ентитети, които се преплитат с обичаите, поверията и фолклора на техните общества. Първичният поглед разкрива, че българската и италианската митологии имат богати традиции на свръхестествени сили и митологични елементи, които са оформили техните култури и разкази през вековете. И както бе отбелязано, въпреки че всяка митология има своите уникални характеристики, между тях има и прилики и споделени мотиви. В настоящия материал, на базата на различни проучвания, ще се направи опит за кратко сравнение и общ анализ върху сходствата и разликите на някои от най-разпространените персонажи съществуващи в българските и италианските народни представи, които са не само съхранени, но живи и днес.*

Ключови думи: *свръхестествено, мит, митология, народни представи, италиански поверия, народни поверия*

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